

Formulation Optimization and Characterisation of Doxycycline Hyclate-Loaded Nanoemulgel for Topical Bacterial Infection

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Abstract

Bacterial infection poses a significant challenge in many critical chronic skin infections, such as diabetic wounds and multidrug-resistant infections. The present study aims to optimise doxycycline hyclate-loaded herbal oil-based nanoemulsion. Various formulations were prepared according to the Box Behnken Design, and particle size, polydispersity index (PDI) and zeta potential were analysed. A stable formulation was loaded in Carbopol 974 (1%) nanoemulgel and evaluated for appearance & drug release. The best formulation was evaluated for ex-vivo permeation efficiency and skin penetration by Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy. The optimised nanoemulsion was found to have a particle size of 24.04 nm, Zeta potential – 10.86mV, and PDI 0.1847. In-vitro drug release studies showed a sustained release pattern over 24 h and followed the Higuchi model ($R^2 = 0.80$) release kinetics. Ex vivo permeation studies revealed that DH-NEG permeates through the membrane at 2.7954 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$, and the conventional gel permeates 1.56 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$. The study concluded that the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulgel formulation has promising application due to its enhanced permeation ability, improved physicochemical stability and above all, it has a sustained drug release profile. The therapeutic efficacy of DH will be improved by the presence of cinnamon oil.

Keywords: Nanoemulgel, Doxycycline hyclate, Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy, Cinnamon oil, Bacterial infection

1. Introduction

Bacterial skin infections are among the most common dermatological conditions seen in clinical practice, affecting individuals of all age groups. If these infections are not treated well, they may cause severe systemic complications or mild, localised lesions to severe. The growing burden of antimicrobial resistance has made treating skin infections more challenging, prompting the need for other approaches that might enhance the therapeutic efficacy while reducing the adverse effects(1). In the last few years, the topical drug delivery methods have gained significant attention since they enable high drug concentration at the infection site, lowering the systemic exposure and related toxicity. Conventional topical formulations, including ointments, creams and lotions, are often used, although they frequently suffer from

limitations like poor drug penetration into deeper layers of the skin, unstable active ingredients and greasy texture that impair patient compliance(2). Inadequate retention on the skin surface, many such formulations also require frequent applications, which may decrease the overall effect of the treatment. These limitations have encouraged researchers to investigate advanced delivery systems that can get beyond these drawbacks(3). Nanotechnology based drug delivery approaches has worked as a solution to overcome these challenges. Nano-emulgels have emerged as a viable platform for topical drug administration, combining the benefits of gels and nanoemulsions into a single system(4).

Nanoemulsions, due to their submicron droplet size, enhance the solubility and permeability of poorly water-soluble drugs, leading to improved penetration through the stratum corneum. Further, loading of nanoemulsions to a gel base, not only do they improve the viscosity, spreadability and ease of application, but also extend the residence time of the formulation on the skin(5). These dual advantages make nanoemulgels suitable for delivering both natural components and synthetic drugs with improved stability and bioavailability(6). The incorporation of natural oils into nanoemulsion offers an additional therapeutic effect. Several plant-derived oils have inherent antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and wound healing properties, which give synergistic effects with synthetic drugs to combat resistant bacterial strains. Additionally, natural oils often have antioxidant properties that help in reducing oxidative stress in infected cells and hastening recovery(7). The combination of a potent synthetic antibacterial drug with a selected herbal oil in a nanoemulgel system represents an innovative approach to address both efficacy and patient acceptability. Several studies have shown the success of such combinations of synthetic drugs with natural oils. For instance, in comparison to traditional formulations, the nanoemulgel containing natural oils like neem, myrrh or tea tree oil has demonstrated improved skin penetration, enhanced antibacterial activity and favourable stability profiles(8,9). Similarly, the topical applications of synthetic drugs like clindamycin, mupirocin, and fusidic acid have resulted in improved therapeutic effects from the usage of nanoemulgel formulations. Despite these developments, there is limited research focusing on the combination use of synthetic antibacterial drugs and specific herbal oils within a single nanoemulgel for targeted treatment of bacterial skin infections(10,11).

The present research aims to formulate, optimise and evaluate a novel nanoemulgel incorporating doxycycline hyclate and cinnamon oil for the treatment of bacterial skin infections. The formulation was developed to harness the synergistic antibacterial effect of both active ingredients, a synthetic drug, doxycycline hyclate and an herbal oil i.e. cinnamon oil, which aid in improving drug penetration through the skin, and improve patient compliance through a stable, non-greasy and easy-to-apply dosage form. The research further aims to investigate the physicochemical characteristics, in vitro release profile and antibacterial efficacy of the developed formulation, providing a scientific basis for its potential use in clinical settings.

2. Materials & Methods

2.1 Materials

Doxycycline hyclate was obtained from Neon Laboratories, Mumbai, India, as a gift sample. Tea tree oil, myrrh oil, cumin oil, cinnamon oil and oregano oil were obtained as a gift sample from Rare Essential Oil, Gurgaon, India. Tween 20, Tween 40, Lecithin, Span 40, Cremophor EL, Ethylene glycol, PEG 400, PEG 600, ethanol, methanol, and propylene glycol were purchased from SD Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India. All the chemicals used for Experimentation were of analytical grade.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Screening of Oil

Oils having antibacterial activity, like tea tree oil, myrrh oil, cumin oil, cinnamon oil and oregano oil, were taken for the development of nanoemulsion. Doxycycline hyclate is a yellow, hygroscopic crystalline powder; therefore, its solubility was analysed by employing the cosolvency approach using methanol as the cosolvent. The excess amount of drug (doxycycline hyclate, approximately 50 mg) was accurately weighed. Then, it will be dissolved in 2 mL of methanol using a vortex for 1 minute, followed by sonication for 5 minutes to ensure complete solubilization. Cinnamon oil (5 mL) was preheated separately to 40°C under constant magnetic stirring at 800 rpm. The methanolic solution of doxycycline was then added to the cinnamon oil dropwise at a rate of approximately 0.1ml/min under continuous stirring to facilitate uniform mixing (12). The resulting mixture was placed overnight on stirring at 40°C in a loosely capped amber glass vial to facilitate the gradual evaporation of methanol. The complete evaporation of methanol was confirmed gravimetrically by recording the weight of the vial at hourly intervals during the final 3 hours of stirring, ensuring a constant weight with a deviation of less than ± 1 mg, indicative of negligible residual solvent(13).

2.2.2 Screening of Surfactant

Five Surfactants, i.e. Tween 20, Tween 60, Tween 80, Span 80, and Cremophor EL, were analysed for nanoemulsion. For each surfactant, a 2.5 % w/w solution was formed in 2.5ml transparent solution, the addition of oil was repeated until a cloudy solution was prepared, and a surfactant able to emulsify the maximum quantity of oil was selected for the nanoemulsion(14).

2.2.3 Screening of Co Surfactant

Propylene glycol, PEG 200, PEG 300 and PEG 400 are the co-surfactants that were analysed for the formulation of nanoemulsion. For each co-surfactant, a 2.5 % w/w solution was formed in 2.5ml of water, and 20 μ L of oil was added under vigorous stirring. The addition of oil was repeated until a cloudy solution was prepared, and a co-surfactant able to emulsify the maximum quantity of oil was selected for the formation of a nanoemulsion(15).

2.2.4 Pseudo-Ternary Phase Diagram Studies

The pseudo-ternary phase diagram studies are used to identify the optimised ratio of the selected surfactant and cosurfactant required for the formulation of nanoemulsion(16). The different ratios of surfactant and cosurfactant (S_{mix} ratio of Cremophor EL and PEG 400) (1:0, 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1 and 5:1) were mixed with selected oil in the ratios (1:9, 1:8, 1:7,1:6, and 2:8), followed by the titration of each mixture of oil and S_{mix} against the water. After each addition of water to the mixture, a visible observation for clarity and turbidity was performed. The systems which seemed transparent and readily flowable were indicated on a pseudo-ternary phase diagram, representing the aqueous phase, the second representing the oil and the third representing the S_{mix} ratio(17).

2.2.5 Preparation of Drug-Loaded Nanoemulsion

DH-loaded nanoemulsion was formulated using the aqueous titration method(18). The method involved the addition of a fixed amount of drug into the glass vial with the necessary amount of oil, followed by the dissolution of the drug in the oil, along with S_{mix} being continuously added. The resulting mixture was microtitrated with distilled water to formulate a coarse droplet emulsion. The ultrasonic processor of 30 kHz was used for 30 to 90 seconds to convert the coarse emulsion into a nanoemulsion(19). Since cavitation from ultrasonication results in heat production, the sonication was performed for seconds(20).

2.2.6 Optimisation of Formulation Components for Nanoemulsion

Ranges of the different components were selected based on the results of the hit-and-trial method. DH – loaded nanoemulsion was optimised using a 3-factor 3-level factorial Box-Behnken experimental design approach (Design Expert 13 version). The independent variables

and their corresponding levels of independence, are listed in **Table 1**. The effect of different concentrations of oil phase, surfactant, co-surfactant and aqueous phase within the chosen ranges were determined on the particle size, PDI, and zeta potential (21).

Table 1. Variables used for the optimisation of Doxycycline hyclate Nanoemulsion using BBD.

Factors	Levels		
Independent variables	Low	Medium	High
X1= Oil (%)	1.11	2.405	3.7
X2= Smix (%)	3.89	12.295	20.7
X3=Stirring Speed RPM)	300	650	1000
Dependent variables			
Y1 = Particle Size (nm)	Minimize		
Y2= Polydispersity Index (PDI)	Minimize		
Y3 = Zeta Potential (Mv)	Optimize		

2.3 Characterisation of Drug-Loaded Nanoemulsion

2.3.1 Physical Appearance

Physical factors like colour, homogeneity and consistency of the formulated nanoemulgel were noticed by visual inspection. Any separation in the formulation was considered as sign of instability of the nanoemulsion.

2.3.2 Particle Size & Polydispersity Determination

The particle size of a nanoemulsion is a critical characteristic since smaller particles will generate more surface area, which will eventually increase the absorption of the drug. The particle size and PDI of the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulsion formulation were determined by using the dynamic light scattering technique (Zetasizer 1000 HAS, Malvern Instruments, Malvern, UK). This technique involved the dilution of the formulation in the ratio 1:9 with double-distilled water, and then it was placed in a quartz cuvette for determination at an angle of 90 ° and maintained temperature of 25°C (22).

2.3.3 Zeta Potential Determination

The zeta potential and surface charge of the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulsion formulation were observed by using the Zeta sizer 1000 HAS, Malvern Instruments, UK. The nanoemulsion formulation was diluted ten times with double-distilled water, then placed in a quartz cuvette for the determination of surface charge (23).

2.3.4 pH, Viscosity

The pH of the DH-loaded nanoemulsion was determined at 25 ± 0.5 °C, by using a previously calibrated digital pH meter (Mettler-Toledo, Langacher, Switzerland) (24). A Brookfield viscometer (DV-III+ Rheometer, Brookfield, WI, USA) was used to measure the viscosity of formulated DH-loaded nanoemulsion by employing a cone and plate at 25 °C and 10 rpm (25).

2.3.5 Drug Content Determination

The drug content of the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulsion formulation was evaluated by dissolving 1ml of the formulation in a suitable quantity (10 mL) of methanol. The mixture was then shaken at 50 rpm for 30 minutes at 37 ± 0.5 °C in an incubator. The supernatant liquid was collected after 30 minutes, then it was analysed by using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) at 275 nm, and methanol was used as a blank (26).

2.3.6 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Fourier transform infrared Spectroscopy of the pure drug and the optimised formulation was performed by using the potassium bromide pellet technique. A homogenous mixture was prepared by using a small amount of pure drug and the lyophilised form of the optimised formulation separately with potassium bromide at a ratio of 1:10, followed by the grinding of

the mixture. Then, a small amount of powdered mixture was taken for compression to thin, semitransparent pellets (film) by applying pressure. The compressed pellets' IR spectrum was assessed between 4500 – 400 cm^{-1} by using an FTIR spectrophotometer (27).

2.4 Preparation of Drug-Loaded Nanoemulgel

2.4.1 Preparation of nanoemulgel

Carbopol 974 was chosen as gel base. 1% Carbopol 974 was added to distilled water using homogenization to disperse it uniformly and to remove air bubbles. The prepared mixture was left overnight for the purpose of swelling and to make a uniform dispersed gel, and the final pH of the gel was adjusted to 5.5 by using triethanolamine.

For nanoemulgel preparation, optimised nanoemulsion was added to the 1% hydrogel matrix at 100 rpm for 10 minutes until a uniform nanoemulgel was prepared (28). Later drug release and drug permeation was evaluated.

2.5.3 In-Vitro Drug Release Studies

An in-vitro drug release study was performed by using a dialysis membrane -60. The dialysis membrane was activated first, to open its pores (29).

Simultaneously, 500 ml of phosphate buffer at pH 7.4 was prepared. The formulated Nanoemulgel was placed in the dialysis bag and then submerged in 50 ml of the release medium in a beaker. The beaker was then shaken in an incubator shaker at 100 rpm and 37°C. To maintain the sink conditions, 2 ml aliquots were withdrawn at specific intervals (0.25, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 12, and 24 hours) and replaced with an equal volume of buffer. The aliquots were analysed by using a UV spectrophotometer at 275nm. Each measurement was performed in triplicate (30).

2.5.7 Ex Vivo Skin Permeation Study

In this study, fresh egg membrane was used in a Franz cell diffusion cell to evaluate the permeation profile of the formulated Nanoemulgel and Conventional gel. The receptor compartment was filled with 10 ml of phosphate buffer saline (pH 7.4) as the diffusion medium, and maintained at a temperature of $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ with constant stirring at 100 rpm (31). At the specific time intervals, a 2ml aliquot was withdrawn and replaced with fresh diffusion medium. The collected aliquots were then filtered, diluted and analysed by UV Spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 275 nm(32).

3. Results

3.1 Screening of Oil

Based on the extensive literature, it was observed that cinnamon oil has potent antibacterial properties, which makes it suitable for antibacterial formulations. So, it was selected as the oil phase, which may provide synergetic antibacterial activity and enhance the therapeutic efficacy of the formulation. With the help of the cosolvency approach, the drug is incorporated into the oil phase. The Solubility of various oils in the drug is depicted in Figure 1A, and it shows the highest solubility in the cinnamon oil, i.e. 89 mg/ml.

3.2 Screening of Surfactant

Tween 20, Tween 60, Tween 80, Span 80, and Cremophor EL were analysed to emulsify the cinnamon oil by the aqueous titration method. Cremophor EL emulsified the most cinnamon oil, and the mixture remained transparent. A surfactant which emulsifies the most cinnamon oil will be able to make a stable nanoemulsion with maximum drug loaded in it. Therefore, Cremophor EL, having a solubility of 45 mg/mL, was selected as the surface-active agent for the development of the nanoemulsion. The results have been shown in Figure 1B.

3.3 Screening of Co Surfactant

Propylene glycol, PEG 200, PEG 300 and PEG 400 are the co-surfactants that were evaluated for the formulation of nanoemulsion. PEG 400 was found to be more soluble in the oil phase, having a solubility of 67mg/mL, as shown in Figure 1C.

Figure 1. Solubility of Doxycycline Hyclate: A) In various oils, B) in surfactants and C) In co-surfactants.

3.4 Pseudo-Ternary Phase Diagram Studies

The pseudo-ternary phase diagram studies are a valuable tool for analysing the optimal composition range of excipients, and this is also used to design the nanoemulsion region. It demonstrates how the volume changes of surfactant (Cremophor EL) or co-surfactant (PEG 400) in different phases affect the system's behaviour, as shown in Figure 2. The analysis of the pseudo-ternary phase diagram showed that, among the different ratios (1:0, 1:1, 2:1, 3:1, 4:1, 5:1) tested, the 5:1 Smix ratio covered the largest area in the oil-in-water (o/w) NE region, making it the preferred choice for further studies.

Figure 2. Pseudo-ternary phase diagrams depicting the existence of o/w nanoemulsion region (dotted region) for different concentrations of surfactants: co-surfactant ratios (or S_{mix})

3.5 Optimisation of Formulation Components for Nanoemulsion

DH – loaded nanoemulsion was optimised via Box Behnken statistical design model. The effect of different concentrations of oil phase, Smix and stirring speed within the chosen ranges on the particle size, PDI, and zeta potential was observed as shown in Table 2 (33).

Table 2: Optimisation table by Design Expert Box Behnken Model

Run	Factor 1 A: Oil % w/w	Factor 2 B: Smix % w/w	Factor 3 C: Stirring Speed rpm	Response 1 Particle Size nm	Response 2 Zeta Potential mv	Response 3 PDI
1	1.11	12.295	300	26	0.346	-13.43
2	2.405	3.89	300	45	0.45	-15.7
3	1.11	3.89	650	15.75	0.304	-13.13
4	3.7	12.295	1000	48	0.483	-14.82
5	2.405	12.295	650	22	0.187	-10.86
6	2.405	20.7	300	19	0.135	-8.2
7	2.405	12.295	650	24.04	0.187	-10.86
8	3.7	12.295	300	57.89	0.421	-15.28
9	2.405	12.295	650	24.1	0.187	-10.86
10	2.405	20.7	1000	15	0.114	-6.33
11	3.7	3.89	650	73	0.498	-19.89
12	3.7	20.7	650	18.4	0.126	-7.57
13	1.11	12.295	1000	17.5	0.124	-7.21
14	2.405	12.295	650	24.3	0.187	-10.85

In graph A1, the actual factor was stirring speed, X1 and X2 were oil and Smix. It shows that by increasing the speed, the particle size increases. As the speed reduced, the size of the particle also decreased, and it differed at different ranges of oil and Smix. The optimal stirring speed was found to be 650 RPM. In graph A2, the factor was Smix and X1 & X2 were taken as oil and stirring speed. As the concentration of Smix varies, the particle size will change. The high concentration of Smix reduced the particle size because a higher concentration of surfactant reduces the surface tension, hence more oil is solubilised, forming smaller particles and increasing emulsification efficiency. The optimal Smix was found to be 12.295. In graph A3, the actual factor was oil and X1 & X2 were taken as Smix and stirring speed. As the concentration of oil increases, it will increase the particle size, and a lower concentration will decrease the particle size (34). The optimal value of oil at optimal speed & Smix were found to be 2.405.

In graph B1, the actual factor was stirring speed, and X1 & X2 were taken as oil and Smix. As the stirring speed increases, PDI will also increase, and as the stirring speed decreases, PDI will also decrease. In graph B2, the actual factor was taken as Smix and X1 & X2 were taken as oil and stirring speed. When the Smix is increased, the PDI will also increase. As the Smix concentration decreased, the PDI also decreased. In graph B3, the actual factor was taken as oil and X1 & X2 were taken as Smix & stirring speed. As the oil concentration decreased, the PDI value also increased. As the concentration of oil increased, the concentration of PDI also decreased. On increasing the concentration of Oil, the PDI increased, which shows a direct relationship keeping other factors constant, as more oil leads to an increase in coalescence formation, resulting in larger droplets of different sizes. However, when the Smix concentration is increased, the PDI will decrease. Because more surfactant covers the surface of globules, decreasing the surface tension at the interface stabilises globules and decreases the coalescence of smaller globules (35).

In graph C1, the actual factor was considered as stirring speed, and X1 & X2 were taken as oil and Smix. As the stirring speed increases, the zeta potential will decrease, and as the stirring speed decreases, the zeta potential will increase. In graph C2, the actual factor was taken as Smix and X1 & X2 were taken as oil and stirring speed. When the concentration of Smix decreases, the zeta potential will increase, and as the concentration of Smix decreases, the value of zeta potential will decrease. In graph C3, the actual factor was considered as oil and X1 & X2 were taken as Smix & stirring speed. As the concentration of oil increases, the zeta potential will decrease, and as the concentration of oil is lowered, the zeta potential will increase. On increasing the oil concentration, the zeta potential increases again towards the negative side. Whereas an increase in the zeta potential owing to increasing oil concentration can be due to adsorption of the ionised forms of polar components of cinnamon oil like eugenol, cinnamic acid, linalool and coumarin containing carboxyl and hydroxyl groups, increasing negative charge on the surface of oil droplets (36).

Figure 3 : Three-dimensional surface plots depicting the interaction effects of (Oil , Smix & stirring speed) independent variables on the particle size (A1, A2, A3) ; PDI (B1, B2, B3); Zeta Potential (C1, C2, C3)

The main objective of the Box Behnken Design was to obtain the optimal formulation components to prepare the nanoemulsion. This design provides the optimised recipe to formulate the formulation and predicts that the formulation must have oil, Smix and sonication time of 2.405%, 12.295% and 650 rpm, respectively. Then, the formulation suggested by the

design was prepared, and it was found that the results of the dependent variables were very close to the results suggested by the design shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Predicted optimised formulation by Design along with experimental results

Response	Predicted Mean	Predicted Median	Observed	Std. Deviation	Data Mean
Particle Size (nm)	23.688	23.688	24.04	1.40528	24.04
PDI	0.187	0.187	0.187	0.0317186	0.187
Zeta Potential	-10.862	-10.862	-10.86	0.675849	-10.86

3.6 Characterisation of Drug-Loaded Nanoemulsion

3.6.1 Physical Appearance

Physical factors like colour, homogeneity and consistency of the formulated nanoemulgel were noticed by visual inspection as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Physical appearance of formulated nanoemulsion

Sr. No.	Parameters	Observation
1	Colour	Light Yellow
2	Homogeneity	Uniform
3	Consistency	Smooth
4	Clarity	Translucent
5	Odour	Mild spicy

3.6.2 Particle Size & Polydispersity Determination

The particle size of a nanoemulsion showed a particle size of 23.688 nm, and a PDI of 0.187 shows that particles are uniformly sized in the prepared formulation. Figure 4A shows the particle size and PDI of the optimized nanoemulsion formulation (DH-NE).

3.6.3 Zeta Potential Determination

The zeta potential and surface charge of the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulsion formulation give an idea of the stability of the nanoemulsion, and it was observed to be - 10.862 mV and a negative value, indicating good formulation stability as shown in Figure 4B. Non-ionic surfactants were selected for the nanoemulsion preparation as they have advantages in terms of stability, compatibility, lower toxicity and non-irritancy as compared to amphoteric or ionic surfactants.

Figure 4. A: Zeta sizer result of particle size; B: Zeta Potential

3.6.4 pH, Viscosity

The pH of the DH-loaded nanoemulsion was determined at a temperature of 25 ± 0.5 °C and was found to be 5.3 ± 0.2 , which is in the range for the topical formulation that is 4 to 6 (37). Therefore, the formulated nanoemulgel is suitable for topical application, without causing any irritation. The viscosity of the optimised formulation was found to be 29 ± 0.47 cps, which is very low. It is a crucial parameter for deciding the stability and efficacious drug release from the nanoemulsion(38).

3.6.5 Drug Content Determination

The drug content of the optimised DH-loaded nanoemulsion formulation was evaluated, and the formulation exhibited a drug content of $97.76 \pm 0.95\%$, indicating a higher drug loading capability, which is an essential characteristic of the nanoemulsion.

3.6.6 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

FTIR analysis was performed to assess the physicochemical interactions between the formulation components and the drug. The results of the FTIR spectrum of the pure drug and optimised Doxycycline Hyclate Nanoemulsion formulation are depicted in Figure 5A, B. The main peaks of the FTIR spectrum of the pure Doxycycline hyclate were at $3326 - 3280$ cm^{-1} (N-H stretching & O-H stretching); $1552-1612$ cm^{-1} (N-H & C=O bending); 1218 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretching & C-N stretching); 1039.00 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching); 991 cm^{-1} (=C-H bending). The FTIR spectrum of the optimised Doxycycline Hyclate NE formulation showed peaks at 3324 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching) & O-H stretching; 1639 cm^{-1} (N-H bending) & C=O bending. There was no major deviation in peaks of the FTIR spectrum for the optimised Doxycycline hyclate formulation and pure doxycycline hyclate drug, which confirmed the absence of molecular interaction between the drug and the formulation components. All the peaks in the FTIR spectrum of the pure drug and the optimised Doxycycline hyclate formulation were present as per the functional groups present in the structure of the drug.

S.No.	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group	FTIR band of doxycycline Hyclate (cm ⁻¹)	FTIR band of the formulation containing DH (cm ⁻¹)
1	~3324 - 3280	O-H/N-H Stretching	~3326-3280	~3324
2	~1552 – 1612	C=O, N-H bending	~1552 – 1612	~1639
3	~1218	C- O-C Stretching or C-N stretching	~1218	-
4	~1039	C-O Stretching	~1039	-
5	~991	=C-H bending	~991	-

Figure 5. A: FTIR spectrum for the pure drug; B: FTIR of DH-NEG Formulation

3.7 Characterisation of Drug-Loaded Nanoemulgel

3.7.1 Physical Appearance

The formulated DH-loaded nanoemulgel was squeezed between the thumb and index finger to check the gel's grittiness and consistency. The formulated nanoemulgel was visually examined for the presence of any lumps, air bubbles or visible foreign particles that would disrupt the homogeneity of the gel shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Physical appearance of formulated nanoemulgel

Sr. No.	Parameters	Observation
1	Colour	Light Yellow
2	Homogeneity	No phase separation or grittiness
3	Consistency	Non-greasy texture
4	Clarity	Slightly opaque
5	Lump Formation	Absent
6	Odour	Mild spicy

3.7.2 In-Vitro Drug Release Studies

In-vitro drug release studies were carried out to compare the Conventional Gel from the DH NEG formulation, shown in Figure 6A. The release kinetics data revealed distinct patterns across the formulations. The NEG released $47.16 \pm 1.79\%$ of the drug within 2 hours, while the CG showed a slower release of $21.96 \pm 2.86\%$ in the same period, likely due to the firm, three-dimensional structure of the NEG as shown in Figure 6A. This double fold increase in the release of DH from the optimised DH NEG formulation compared to could be attributed to the presence of the drug in gel, owing to the reduced droplet size, which will provide an increased surface area for drug dissolution and an increase in the surface area leads to an increase in the dissolution rate as suggested by the Noyes – Whitney Equation. The drug release of the conventional gel is poorer than that of the optimised nanoemulgel formulation, which is attributed to the low aqueous solubility of the drug, the coarse particle size and the presence of the drug in the crystalline form(39). As a result, DH NEG formulation boosted the solubility of

the drug as well as the dissolution rate due to the reduced droplet size of the nanoemulgel formulation.

3.7.3 Ex-Vivo Skin Permeation Study

The ex-vivo drug release experiment was performed using a hairless rat skin sample. After the period of 8 hours, the total drug release was recorded as $54.85 \pm 1.97\%$ for DH-NEG and $30.85 \pm 1.87\%$ for DH-Conventional Gel. Flux, which refers to the amount of drug that permeates through a membrane per unit time, was also calculated as $2.7954 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$ for DH- NEG and $1.56 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$ for DH- Conventional Gel. The permeation coefficient, determined by dividing the flux by the total amount of drug in the donor compartment ($5000 \mu\text{g Na}$), was calculated to be 0.6988 for DH-NEG and 0.3915 for DH-Conventional Gel. The results were visually presented in Figure 6B.

Figure 6. A: In vitro drug release comparison of optimized DH -NEG formulation with DH-CG formulation; B: Ex vivo drug release comparison of DH-NEG formulation with DH-CG formulation.

4. Conclusions

Nanoemulgel formulations are suitable for topical application and in case of chronic infections and wounds where there are chances of getting tolerance to treatment can be better treated by nanoemulgel. They help in penetration of drug across the skin layers and presence of natural oil as a component of nanoemulgel could also help synergistically in fighting with infection. While developing drug loaded nanoemulsion, it is necessary to ensure the stability of the formulation. Optimized nanoemulsion loaded Carbopol gel was developed and evaluated for appearance, viscosity, drug content, and drug release. The drug release profile of the nanoemulgel showed a sustained release pattern over 24 h and showed Higuchi model ($R^2 = 0.80$) release kinetics. Ex-vivo skin permeation studies demonstrated almost doubled permeation of Doxycycline hyclate nanoemulgel through the egg membrane as compared to the conventional gel. Therefore, we can conclude that nanoemulgel formulation have promising application in skin infections due to its enhanced permeation ability, improved physicochemical stability and a sustained drug release profile.

Conflicts of interest statement

Authors declare no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Author's contribution

The authors confirm their contribution to the paper: study conception and design: Dr Jayamanti Pandit, data collection, draft manuscript: Neha Bhamboo, Analysis and interpretation of data:

Neha Bhamboo, Dr Jayamanti Pandit, review of the first draft: Ashutosh Upadhayay, Yogendra Singh. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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